

Synthesis and ion exchange behavior of acrylonitrile-based zirconium phosphate – A new hybrid cation exchanger

K. G. Varshney and Altaf Hussain Pandith*

Department of Applied Chemistry, Faculty of Engineering & Technology, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh-202 002, India

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Acrylonitrile-based zirconium phosphate (AcZP) has been prepared as a new hybrid cation exchange material. Out of a large number of samples prepared, the one selected for detailed studies has an Na⁺ i.e.c. equal to 2.08 meq/dry g. This new material has been characterized on the basis of its physicochemical analysis like X-ray, IR, SEM, thermal stability, and ion exchange studies. Distribution coefficient (K_d) values for various metal ions in different solvents have been determined to explore its separation potential. The material shows a marked selectivity for strontium. The material may have some applications in the removal of strontium from aqueous nuclear waste.

The preparation of hybrid materials in which organic molecules are covalently bound to phosphate and phosphonate groups of tetravalent metals such as Ti and Zr is opening interesting perspectives^{1,2}. The reason is that a variety of materials with desired functionalities can be designed from the different linking of $M_{(iv)}O_6$ octahedra and O_3 PR tetrahedra which can be further modified by ion exchange and/or intercalation. The organic moieties can be located inside the solid, bridging across layers or at its surface giving rise to non-bridged organic spacer inside an inorganic matrix, can be performed when at least two covalent bonds are formed between the organic molecule and the solid. Acrylonitrile has recently been used as a major constituent in many synthetic hybrid and fibrous ion exchange materials^{2,3}. Because of its promising characteristics as a crosslinking and binding agent, acrylonitrile as an organic moiety has been incorporated in amorphous zirconium phosphate host material.

The present work describes the synthesis and characterization of this new hybrid material, acrylonitrile-based zirconium phosphate. This material is highly selective for strontium and may have some potential applications in the removal of strontium from aqueous nuclear waste.

Results and Discussion

Acrylonitrile-based zirconium phosphate (AcZP) appears to be a promising hybrid material with good ion exchange characteristics. The ion exchange capacity (i.e.c. in meq. g⁻¹, dry basis) for the various metal ions is as follows: Li⁺, 1.87; Na⁺, 2.08; K⁺, 2.25; Mg²⁺, 1.20; Ca²⁺, 1.75; Sr²⁺, 2.50.

The most interesting feature of this material is its superiority over similar hybrid materials prepared earlier⁴. The Na⁺ i.e.c. (meq/dry g) after heating the material at various

temperatures for 1 h each are as follows: 2.08 (60°), 2.08 (100°), 1.75 (300°), 1.32 (500°), 0.80 (700°), 0.50 (800°), 0.00 (900°). The results reveal that the material does not lose its i.e.c. upto 100°. An appreciable i.e.c. is retained (24%) even upon heating it upto 800° which is an important feature. The mixed oxides produced on heating the material upto such a high temperature are perhaps converted into their hydrated forms when treated with water giving rise to observed ion exchange capacity. Chemical stability of the material is also observed to be quite high. The results indicate that only a negligible amount of the exchanger is dissolved in various solvents (1–4 M HCl, 1–4 M HNO₃, 1–4 M H₂SO₄, 0.1 M KOH, 0.5–0.1 M NaOH, 0.5–1.0 M NH₄OH, 1–2 M KNO₃) out of the 200 mg taken for its chemical stability test. The material also shows reproducibility in properties as is evident from the fact that AcZP prepared in various batches does not show any appreciable deviation in its exchange properties.

The column elution experiments indicate a dependence of the rate of elution on the concentration of the eluant which is an usual behavior for such materials. Sodium nitrate solution of 1.4 M conc. is found to be essential for the complete removal of H⁺ ions from a column containing one gram of the exchanger. The remarkable increase in the conc. of the eluant needed for complete elution in comparison to other similar materials may be due to an appreciable amount of dipolar interaction contributed by acrylonitrile moiety in the material.

The pH-titration curves obtained under equilibrium conditions are shown in Fig. 1. For LiOH/LiCl, NaOH/NaCl and KOH/KCl systems which indicate a monofunctional exchange process, the material releases H⁺ ions easily with the addition of metal salt solutions to the system. The strong

Fig. 1 Equilibrium pH-titration curves of acrylonitrile-based zirconium phosphate.

ion exchange characteristic of this material is evident from the low pH values (~3) of the system when no OH⁻ ions were added to it. Forward and reverse pH-titration curves obtained under non-equilibrium conditions (Fig. 2) are different from those obtained under equilibrium conditions. The reason may be that the ion exchange process is incomplete under non-equilibrium conditions. In neutral medium,

Fig. 2. Non-equilibrium pH-titration curves of acrylonitrile-based zirconium phosphate.

the ion exchange capacity is in the order, Li⁺ < Na⁺ < K⁺, as is evident from the pH values at lower hydroxide concentrations. The higher pH values for Li⁺-H⁺ exchange than Na⁺-H⁺ exchange at all OH⁻ conc. suggest that the exchange rate for Li⁺ ion is lower than Na⁺ and K⁺ ions. This obser-

Fig. 3 Histograms showing the elution behaviour of acrylonitrile-based zirconium phosphate.

vation goes together with the fact that the ion exchange occurs by the diffusion of hydrated counter ions into the ion exchange matrix (hydrated radii, Li⁺>Na⁺>K⁺).

An overall higher ion exchange capacity for all the three metal ions in the batch process than in the column process, as suggested by potentiometric curves, may be due to the presence of alkali hydroxide which facilitates the ion exchange by the removal of H⁺ ions from the external solution in accordance with the Le Chatelier's principle.

The IR, X-ray and SEM studies were performed in order to investigate the structural aspects of the material. The IR spectrum confirms the presence of the external water molecules in addition to the OH⁻ groups and the metal oxide present internally in the material. A sharp peak at 1670 and a broad one at 3500 cm⁻¹ indicate the strongly hydrogen bonded OH or coordinated water molecules in addition to the presence of water of crystallization⁵. The broad peak at 1080–1192 cm⁻¹ represents the C–N bending and C–N stretching positions in addition to PO₄³⁻ and HPO₄²⁻ groups⁵. Metal-oxygen stretch and C–N, C–H vibrations are indicated by peaks at 550 and 852 cm⁻¹.

The chemical composition data indicate the molar ratio of Zr^{IV}, acrylonitrile and PO₄³⁻ groups in the material as 8 : 1 : 14. The SEM and X-ray studies suggest that AcZP is a semicrystalline material. Hence an exact description of the crystallographic location of the exchange sites may not be possible. However, on the basis of its ion exchange char-

Table 1. Synthesis of AcZP varying the concentrations of $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ and H_3PO_4

Sample no.	Concentration (M)		Yield	Na ⁺ -ion exchange capacity meq/dry g
	Zr ⁴⁺	PO ₄ ³⁻ %		
S-1	0.1	0.1	23.70	1.90
S-2	0.1	0.2	28.50	1.92
S-3	0.1	0.5	35.20	2.04
S-4	0.2	0.1	30.20	1.51
S-5	0.2	0.5	38.20	1.94
S-6	0.5	0.1	27.30	1.38
S-7	0.5	0.2	29.00	1.43

acteristics and IR spectrum, we may say that this material has a layered structure in which each acrylonitrile molecule is covalently bonded to two phosphate groups pointing towards the interlayer cavities. The ion exchange capacity is due to the exchangeable protons associated with both the phosphate and the acrylonitrile groups.

The distribution studies (Table 2) indicate that the material is highly selective for strontium in comparison to other metal ions studied in different solvent systems. This behavior can be useful in the removal of strontium from aqueous nuclear wastes.

Table 2. K_d Values of some metal ions on AcZP in (demineralized water) DMW, perchloric acid, nitric acid, hydrochloric acid and sulfuric acid

Metal ions	$\times 10^{-2} K_d$				
	DMW	0.1 M HNO ₃	0.1 M HClO ₄	0.1 M HCl	0.1 M H ₂ SO ₄
Na ^I	6.00	10.00	6.00	7.50	10.7
K ^I	16.60	5.99	16.77	22.1	6.00
Mg ^{II}	3.33	7.77	16.77	6.00	10.00
Ca ^{II}	16.77	30.00	6.00	5.99	22.10
Sr ^{II}	99.00	70.50	70.50	99.00	70.50
Ba ^{II}	30.00	6.00	16.77	7.79	16.77
Cr ^{III}	43.40	30.00	16.77	10.00	16.77
Mn ^{II}	30.00	6.00	1.34	1.34	1.00
Zn ^{II}	16.00	4.00	4.00	7.50	7.50
Cd ^{II}	43.40	10.00	16.70	5.99	5.99
Hg ^{II}	99.00	22.00	3.33	33.33	10.70
Pb ^{II}	70.00	16.70	30.00	30.00	6.00

Experimental

Zirconyl chloride ($ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$) and all other chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

Instruments used : Elico LI-10 pH meter, Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer, GBC 902 atomic absorption spectrometer, Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer, Philips

PW-1700 X-ray diffractometer, Nicolet 5DX IR (KBr) spectrophotometer, Stereoscan 250 MK III scanning electron microscope. A shaker incubator ($\pm 0.5^\circ$) was used for equilibrium studies.

Solutions of zirconium oxychloride and orthophosphoric acid were prepared in demineralized water (DMW). Acrylonitrile solutions were prepared in ethanol.

Synthesis of the ion exchanger : A number of samples were prepared by mixing aqueous solutions of zirconyl chloride, orthophosphoric acid and ethanolic solutions of acrylonitrile (20, 30 and 50%) in different volume ratios as follows.

To a mixture of ethanolic solution of acrylonitrile and aqueous zirconyl chloride solution (0.1 M), a solution of orthophosphoric acid (0.1 M) was slowly added at 70–80° with stirring. The resulting gel was aged in the mother liquor for 24 h at room temperature and filtered by suction. The excess acid was then removed by washing with DMW till the pH of the washing was ~6 and dried (60°). The dried granulated gel was then converted into the H⁺ form by treating with 1 M HNO₃ for 24 h. Finally, the material was washed with water, dried and sieved for further studies. The sample having Zr^{IV} : acrylonitrile : PO₄³⁻ mixing ratio of 1 : 2 : 2 was found to possess the maximum ion exchange capacity (1.80 meq/dry g). Various samples of this material were, therefore, prepared by changing the concentrations of zirconyl chloride and orthophosphoric acid solutions, while maintaining the strength of acrylonitrile solution at 30% (Table 1). Finally, sample S-3 was selected for further studies on the basis of its highest Na⁺ ion exchange capacity.

Ion exchange capacity (i.e.c.) : The ion exchange capacity was determined by the usual column process by taking 1.00 g of the exchanger (H⁺-form) in a column (i.d. ~1 cm) fitted with glasswool at the bottom. A 1 M metal ion solution (250 ml) was used as eluant, maintaining a very slow flow rate (~0.5 ml min⁻¹). The effluent was titrated against a standard alkali solution to determine the total H⁺ ions released.

The Na⁺ i.e.c. was also checked directly by displacement with 1 M HNO₃ solution and indirectly by measuring the amount of Na⁺ present in the effluent when an H⁺-form exchange column was eluted with 1 M NaNO₃ solution (250 ml). The measurement was performed by an Elico CL-360 flame photometer, after making the appropriate dilutions.

Effect of eluant concentration on the i.e.c. : NaNO₃ solution (250 ml) of varying concentrations (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6 M) were passed through a column containing the exchanger (1 g) in the H⁺-form with a flow rate of 0.5 ml min⁻¹. The H⁺ ions eluted were titrated against

0.1 M NaOH solution. The optimum concentration of the eluant for a complete elution of H⁺ ions in 250 ml was found to be 1.4 M.

Elution behavior : The column containing the material in the H⁺-form (1 g) was eluted with 1 M NaNO₃ solution (250 ml) having a standard flow rate of 0.5 ml min⁻¹ and fractions (10 ml) of the effluent were collected. They were titrated for the H⁺ ions released against a standard NaOH solution. This experiment was conducted to find out the minimum volume necessary for a complete elution of the H⁺ ions, reflecting the efficiency of the column. The result is shown Fig. 3.

pH-titration :

(a) **Equilibrium process** : Equimolar solutions of alkali metal chlorides and their hydroxides in different volume ratios were added separately to the exchanger (500 mg) in H⁺-form. Its final volume was 50 ml and ionic strength constant. The pH of the solution was recorded after every 24 h until the equilibrium was attained after 4 days. The pH at equilibrium was plotted against the milli-equivalents of the OH⁻ ions added.

(b) **Non-equilibrium process** : The exchanger (500 mg) was mixed with 0.012 M salt solution (NaCl, KCl and LiCl; 100 ml). The mixture was kept for 1 h and titrated against 0.012 M solutions of the respective alkali, recording the pH of the solution after each addition of 1.6 ml of the titrant till the pH became constant. The back-titration was then carried out by adding the same fractions of 0.012 M HNO₃ to the solution.

Composition : The powdered sample (100 mg) was dissolved in a minimum amount of conc. HF. The solution was then evaporated to dryness, diluted to 100 ml with DMW, and analyzed for zirconium⁶ and phosphate⁷ spectrophotometrically. C, H and N were determined.

Chemical stability : To determine the extent of dissolution of the material in different solutions, the sample (250 mg) was treated with each solution (20 ml) for 24 h at room temperature. The mixture was shaken intermittently to obtain equilibrium and supernatant liquid was analyzed quantitatively for Zr^{IV} and PO₄³⁻ contents. Zirconium was determined by atomic absorption spectrometry and phosphate

spectrophotometrically.

Distribution studies : The exchanger (200 mg) in H⁺-form was taken in different metal ion solutions (20 ml) in the required medium and kept for 24 h with intermittent shaking to attain equilibrium. The initial metal ion concentration (0.001 M) in the solution was so adjusted that it did not exceed 3% of the total material. The determinations before and after equilibrium were carried out volumetrically using EDTA as the titrant⁸. The concentration of alkali metal ions was determined by flame photometer. The distribution coefficient (K_d) was then calculated.

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